
LEARNING PROBLEMS IN THE USE OF ENGLISH VOWELS BY UKWUANI AND URHOBOS USERS OF ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

This study is an investigation of the learning problems in the Use of English vowels by Ukwuani and Urhobo users of English. In this research, the transfer features in the spoken English of Ukwuani and Urhobo users is accounted for using generative phonology as the theoretical model. Through qualitative and careful observation data is collected using a micro recorder. The format for transcription is the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA). Using the Distinctive Feature Theory, the diphthongs of Ukwuani and Urhobo languages are examined. The problems of using English vowels by Ukwuani and Urhobo speakers of English are x-rayed. It is discovered that stress is the preserve of English language while tone is the preserve of Ukwuani and Urhobo Languages. This confirms the fact that Nigerian languages are tonal languages. It is therefore, revealed in this study that there are transfer features in the spoken English of Ukwuani and Urhobo users of English. The study also discovers that the phenomenon of tone is a minimal cause of interference. The research concludes by tabulating the problems encountered by Ukwuani and Urhobo users of English based on the levels of difficulty and suggests ways of overcoming them. Apart from linguists, educationists will find this work beneficial in the areas of preparation of educational materials and lesson notes. Nigerian newscasters will also find the work useful since they need to use a variety of Nigerian English that meets international intelligibility. More also, those who use the electronic and print media such as pastors and other clergy, dramatists will find this work useful since they need to improve on their variety to achieve international intelligibility and national acceptability at the same time.

Keywords: Learning Problems, English Vowels Ukwuani, Urhobo, language, Users of English

INTRODUCTION

According to Wikipedia Online (2023), there are over 525 native languages spoken in Nigeria. Translators without borders (2023) put it at over 500 languages. They state that Nigeria is one of the most linguistically diverse countries in the world. World Population Review (2023) puts it at 520 languages spoken in Nigeria today. World Atlas (2023) says Nigeria is a multilingual nation with over 520 languages being spoken in the country.

Worldbook Encyclopedia (2018) says that the language situation in Nigeria is one of the highest instances of language diversity in any country on earth. The new policy is to promote the use of local or native languages, but implementation remains uncertain. Wilsoncenter.org (2023) maintains that with more than 300 ethnic groups, over 500 languages, and many distinct religious and regional differences, it is also one of world's most culturally diverse countries.

Prior to the advent of Europeans to Nigeria, the multiplicity of languages was not a problem. Contact among the different ethnicity that occupies the landmass now called Nigeria was somewhat limited because intercommunication was pretty difficult. The reason being that one can only communicate with another from a different ethnic group only if one can speak that language. This is called mutual intelligibility.

With the advent of the Europeans, contacts among the different ethnic groups increased and sped up with the imposition of the English Language in Nigeria. Therefore, English became very important. However, the importance of English in this sense is limited particularly because when compared with its importance as a medium of international communication, English language in Nigeria is internationally unintelligible. In the words of Crystal (1999:30),

A language, which has come to be spoken by as many people as English has ceased to be the property of any of its constituent communities. Nobody owns English now, not the British, with whom the language began, nor the Americans, who now comprise its largest mother-tongue community.

Crystal's words emphasizes on the importance of English language and the need for it to meet international standard and mutual intelligibility. However, this desire is far from being achieved considering the multilingual state of Nigeria and the inevitability and profusion of interference. Afolayan (1972:6) writes that:

At the opposite extreme are interference varieties that are so widespread in a community and of such long standing that they may be thought stable...

The Urhobo and Ukwuani users of English are not immune to this interference problem. Obviously, interference affects the speech of both the educated and uneducated. English had to be modified by L₂ speakers of English to accommodate the Nigerian cultural elements which were non-cognate to the L₂. According to Osakwe (2005), a domestication process had set in for English. It had to integrate the modern Nigerian/World culture (C₁) and the L₁. The L₁ interference gave the L₂ a new African flavour spoken more like a Nigerian language than a European intonation language that it is. The use of the L₂suprasegmental phonemes to show contrasts or feelings was no longer considered necessary for intelligibility within the community. Each of the L₁ groups spoke the L₂ with some interference features typifying

prominence. Therefore, MP is used as a supporting framework to handle stress. The use of MP is based on the fact that GP is inadequate in handling issues concerned with stress (Robert St Clair: 1)

Literature Review

Linguistic interference has various synonyms such as cross-linguistic influence, language transfer, language mixing, MT interference and so on. This occurs when a speaker applies knowledge from his MT to the learning or usage of a second language. This application of previous knowledge is called transfer of language. Language transfer from Mother Tongue (L_1) to second language (L_2) is known as facilitation. However, when the transfer is negative, the term used is interference. Therefore, for interference to take place, it must involve two languages. This is affirmed by Carl James (1980: 4) below:

...Three branches of two-valued (2 languages are involved) inter-lingual linguistic: translation theory which is concerned with the processes of text conversion: error analysis; and contrastive analysis – the last two having as their object of enquiring the means whereby a monolingual learns to be bilingual.

In the light of the above statement, this research intends to adopt inputs from these “three branches of two valued interlingua linguistic” Carl (1996:143), explaining the language awareness (LA) of bilinguals, emphasize that:

It is here where the contrastive dimension comes to the fore, since one of the determinant of the perceptual salience of an FL item must be its relationship to its MT equivalent especially when the learner already has LA of that MT item.

It is generally believed that modern CA started in 1957 with the work of Robert Lado, (1957) This is why Mowarin (2004: 24) states that “Robert Lado’s Publication of 1957 however, marked the beginning of modern contrastive analysis”. But after Robert Lado, there was Di Pietro, Robert (1971) who identifies Grandgent’s book on the German and English sound systems. James further mentions Weinrich (1953) and Haugen (1953) who undertook studies of immigrant bilingualism. Though, the works of Weinreich and Haugen were not seen as real works of C.A, due to directionality, Carl came to their defense.

As Wikipedia online (2023) puts it, contrastive analysis is the systematic study of a pair of languages with a view to identifying their structural differences and similarities. Historically, it has been used to establish language genealogies.

World Englishes (2023) asserts that in linguistics, the term contrastive analysis refers to “a theoretically grounded, systematic and synchronic comparison of usually two languages...

According to Richards (2023) the contrastive analysis hypothesis (CA), states that where the first language and the target language are similar, learners will generally acquire structures with ease, and where they are different, learners will have difficulty. CA was based on the related theory of language transfer: difficulty in second language learning results from transfer of features of the first language to the second language. Transfer was considered the main explanation for learners’ errors.

C.A, in its core sense, can be defined as the theoretically grounded systematic and synchronic comparison of usually two languages, or at most no more than a small number of languages with a view to ascertaining areas of differences and similarities and helping learners cope with the challenges of second language learning.

DISTINCTIVE FEATURE THEORY

Centrally, one may say that the idea behind distinctive feature theory contrasts between phonemes and this can be as Daniel C. and Jeff Mielk (2017) put it, “be most elegantly and insightfully described in terms of properties of segments rather than by treating segments as alphabetic atoms.” Wikipedia (2023) say in linguistics, a distinctive feature is the most basic unit of phonological structure that distinguishes one sound from another within a language.

Distinctive Feature Theory is an effort to identify the phonetic dimensions that are important for lexical contrasts and phonological patterns in human languages. The set of features and its explanatory role have both expanded over the years, with feature being used to define not only the contrasts but the groupings of sounds involved in rules and phonotactic restrictions, as well as the changes involved in rules (Mielke, 2017).

Metrical Phonology

THE UKWUANI LANGUAGE

The account of the Free Encyclopedia Online (2023) asserts that Ukwuani, a minor group, is also classified as a member of the Igboid language. Ukwuani people share boundaries with the Isoko, the Urhobo, Ika, the Igbo and Ijaw. It is one of the indigenous languages spoken in the Niger Delta region. Ukwuani language and culture is deeply rooted in cultural activities. Scholars of Ukwuani descent have in recent times drawn attention to the fact that it is an endangered language owing to the decline of its native speakers by way of acculturation and urbanization and I believe them. For example, recently I was carrying out a research on the semiotic analysis of some aspects of the culture of Ukwuani people and I had to call my home in order to get a record of ancient poems and tales. Unfortunately, all the persons I placed a call to could not help me. Their response was that they do not know any poem or tale in Ukwuani. Another alarming situation is that even my own children two of them do not speak Ukwuani all because of the dominance of English language and the Nigerian pidgin.

THE URHOBOLANGUAGE

The Urhobo language is spoken by the Urhobo people. The Urhobo who constitute the largest ethnic group in Delta State live in the Western part of the Niger Delta South of the Latitude 6⁰N (Albert Aweto: 3). The Urhobo language belongs to the large group of the Benue-Congo languages. The languages under this grouping are those that share common linguistic characteristics. In Peter Eke’s (2005: 29) words “...languages in this family, such as Edo and Urhobo are deemed to belong to the pool of languages that have contributed to the expansion of Bantu languages...” “Edo” occupies its own position in Williamson’s sub-classification where it is termed ‘Edoid’. Urhobo belongs to the Southwestern Edoid language (SWE). Other languages of the group are Eruwa, Isoko, Okpe and Uvwie.

Just like Ukwuani, the Urhobo language is believed to be endangered. Mowarin (2005: 524) writes of Urhobo stating that “...language endangerment... threatens the three constituent languages of Urhobo culture namely, Urhobo, Okpe and Uvwie”. He gives the factors militating against the Urhobo language as the influence of the Nigerian pidgin, the English language, languages of ethnic groups such as Ukwuani and Ijaw encircling the Urhobos, and

the flawed national language policy modernization or urbanization among other factors. Inter-ethnic marriages is also a contributing factor to language endangerment. I am an Urhobo married to a Yoruba lady. We speak English language and Nigerian Pidgin at home. This makes it difficult for any of my children aged between 20 and 03 to use any of both languages: Urhobo and Yoruba effectively.

Vowels

A vowel is a syllabi speech sound pronounced without any stricture in the vocal tract. Vowels are one of the two principal classes of speech sounds, the other being the consonant. Vowels vary in quality, in loudness and also in quantity (Wikipedia online, 2023). Grammarly.com (2023) defines it as letters that represent speech sounds where air leaves the mouth without any blockage by the tongue, lips or throat.

Methodology

Here we shall establish the phonemes of both Ukwani and Urhobo languages. We shall do this using the concepts of minimal pairs, minimal sets, complementary distribution and free variation.

Establishing the Phonemes of Ukwani and Urhobo Languages

Compared to Urhobo, Yoruba Igbo and Hausa Ukwani language is yet to be fully investigated to a large extent. The phonemes of a language can be established through a number of ways. They include: minimal pair, minimal set, complementary distribution and free variation.

A phoneme is the minimal distinctive linguistic sound. Minimal pair and minimal set have contrastive value because they establish an opposition that keeps apart the two words being contrasted.

Minimal Set

Minimal set are group of sounds that establish opposition that keeps the two words being contrasted apart. Through minimal set the following sounds were established in Ukwani:

nno – salt	onu – neck	inu – story
asa – fish	esa – seven	nsa – fine
uku – waist	oku – conflict	nnku – alcohol
ogwe – tree trunk	ogbe – street	igbe – creep
egbe – gum	egbe – gourd	enyi – object
uka – church	oka – a type of bird	uka – corner
di – husband	di – bear	di – be around
chi – rule	chi – judge	chi – returned

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Examples from the Urhobo language are as follows:

Akpa – unripe	Akpe – tobacco safe	Akpo – life
Orhan – witchcraft	orhe – rumour	orhen – native chalk
Ukpe – bed	ekpe – sand	ekpen – lion
Ovie – king	ovie – slave	ovie - cry
Ofa – filter	Ofe - asthma	ofe - beetle
Ogba – hero	ogban – trumpet	ogba – fence
Ega - worship	oga – sickness	egan - barren
Evu – stomach	evuu – store	eva - alligator

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Minimal Pair

A minimally phonologically distinctive pair of words establishes a minimal distinctive linguistic sound, known as a phoneme, from among the acoustically distinguishable sounds in a language, known as the phones of the language. In other words, any two words that help in discovering which sounds have contrastive value in a given language are said to form a minimal pair. The criteria is that the word being contrasted must have the same number of sounds. That is, the sounds should be identical with the exception of the contrasting sound that should be distributed in the same context in both words. A minimal distinctive sound is one which can distinguish one word from another when all other sounds are identical. These phones are said to be in contrastive distribution. To establish the phoneme of a language such minimal pairs, two words differing in just one distinguishable sound (hence “minimal”), must be found for all the phonemes. If one cannot find a minimal pair or minimal set, the phone are said to be in non-contrastive distribution. They may be in free variation or complementary distributions.

The following sounds are contrasted using minimal pair in Ukwuani

ekwa – egg	ekwa – cry
egwu – dance	egwu – fear
ukor – scarcity	ukor – clothes
ohun – cooked	ohun – death
fi – twist	fi – wash one’s face
chi – rule	chi – judge
ude – cream	udo – peace
oke – boundary	ike – buttocks
ke – for	ke – what?
akai – suffering	ikai – stone
da – fall	di – be around
oka – maize	oka – a type of bird

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Urhobo examples are:

Emu – food	Umu – medicine
Ogho – branch	Ogho - respect
Oko – canoe	Oko – friend
Obe – book	Obo – hand
Erin – fish	Erhi – spirit
Oja – suffering	Oja – stick for staking yam or for covering a fish pond.

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Complementary Distribution

Complementary distribution indicates that two basic sounds are not independent phonemes, but condition variants of the same phoneme, of the same minimally distinctive sound. Non-contrastive variants of a phoneme are called allophones. An allophone is one of the non-contrastive variations of a minimally distinctive linguistic sound. Sounds are in complementary distribution when one occurs under condition A but never B, while the other occurs under condition B but never A. That is, the allophonic variation is predictable from the environment. For example, aspirated phones are allophones of non-aspirated phones in English but comprise phonemes that are allophonic are discovered in a language. The following examples are obtainable in Ukwuani:

Ejeh – aspirated (final)
Echi – unaspirated (medial)
Aha – aspirated (medial)
Okwocha – unaspirated (medial)

Free Variation

Two sounds do not represent two separate phonemes if they are in free variation, that is, if one may use one in any position you may use the other without any semantic effect. For example, aspiration may be omitted from stops at the end of words in English, too; however, whether it is dropped or not is indifferent; the meaning of the word does not change.

On the other hand when we compare different realizations of one and the same phoneme by various speakers in the speech of one and the same person in different situations (that is context free), then the sounds or phonemes are in free variation or random variations. Here we talk of same phoneme in free variation without change in meaning. These are known as allophones. Examples in Ukwuani include:

Ajeh, ejeh (greeting)
Awo, ewo (clothing)
Akwo, ekwo (door)
Ekemu, akamu (corn custard)
Ela, era (insane)
Ulle, ure (lazy)
Nmili, nmiri (water)
Efor, afor (stomach)
Eforafor (name of a community)
Akwa, ekwa (foam)
Efifia, afifia (grass)
Akwukwo, ekwukwor (book)
Eziza, aziza (broom)
Efere, afere (plate)

Allophones are not many in Urhobo language. The most common one is N and L which occur in free variation as seen in the following examples:

Une, ule – song
One, ole – yam
Unurhoro, ulurhoro – threshold or doorstep.

Based on the existence of the Ukwuani vowels discussed above, the Ukwuani vowels chart is presented as follows:

Figure 1: Ukwuani Vowel Chart (extract from Omenogor, 2014)

Some Basic Facts about Ukwuani Vowels

Research has revealed that Ukwuani has nine vowels. This is different from other languages that form a cluster with Igbo because those other languages have eight vowels. Armstrong (1967) and Williamson (1968) have affirmed this fact. They declare that it is nine vowel phonemes are divided into two harmonic sets as given below:

Set 1	Set 2
[i], [u]	[ɪ], [ʊ]
[e], [o]	[ɛ], [ɔ]

Set one vowels are called Advanced Tongue Root Vowels [+ATR] while set two is called Retraced Tongue Root Vowels [-ATR] based on the operation which is obtainable within vowel harmony in a language. Vowel harmony is an account of the phonological situations where vowels of a specific language can be classified into two sets. Ukwuani is to some extent a harmony language because the vowel of any given word can be selected from the two sets available in Ukwuani. However, [a] is a neutral vowel in the Ukwuani sound system in that it does not belong to any of the set of the vowels that co-occur. Investigation has proven that [a] can co-occur with either set one or set two vowel phonemes. Nevertheless, the most correct thing to say is that Ukwuani vowel system displays partial vowel harmony and that vowel [a], much as it is true that it co-occurs more frequently with set two vowels, also co-occurs with set one vowels.

Aziza (2007: 276-277) observation on vowel harmony system of languages substantiates our position on the status of Ukwuani vowel harmony as follows:

Some languages have complete vowel harmony while some others have partial vowel harmony. In a system with complete vowel harmony, all the vowels of a word, including its affixes come from a particular set. On the other hand, in a system with partial vowel harmony, there are instances where the vowels of one set mix with the vowels of the other set.

Urhobo Vowels

The Urhobo vowels are basically seven. The seven vowels correspond with the seven letters in the orthography. Therefore, the sounds correspond with the seven letters and so there is no divergence between sounds and letters. As an Edoid language, most of the languages here saw a reduction from 10 vowel system to seven vowel system. Only Degema language still retains ten vowel system. Aziza (2007: 779) quoting Elugbe and others states that Isoko, an SWE language has nine vowels with no /ə/. Although Urhobo does not have diphthongs apart from /ai/, it has sequences whose underlying representation involves phonological processes that produce glide formation (GF).

As said earlier, Urhobo has seven vowels however, scholars have recognized nine at the underlying level to include /e/ and /o/ having a split. Like the English vowels, Urhobo vowels are syllabic. It operates a syllabification rule that inserts a syllabic boundary after each vowel segment (Aziza 2007: 80). The future, “tense” has the (-) value for all the vowels. This indicates that none of the Urhobo vowel is a long vowel. Three heights are specified for the vowels and these are “high”, “low” and “mid”. Since we are using the binary system, the feature “mid” is not presented in our discussions. Below is the vowel chart of Urhobo

Table 2: Vowel Chart in Urhobo

	I	e	ɜ	A	ɔ	O	U
Syllabic	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
High	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
Low	-	-	±	+	±	-	-
Front	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
Back	-	-	-	-	+	+	+
Round	-	-	-	-	+	+	+
Tense (Long)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Data Analysis

An examination of the phoneme inventories of Ukwuani and Urhobo vowels indicate that while Ukwuani has nine, Urhobo has seven, though there is still a controversy as to the actual figure. Ukwuani has only monophthongs whereas Urhobo has both monophthong and diphthongs. Vowel length does not occur both in Ukwuani and Urhobo as it is the case in English. Moreso, central vowels do not occur both in Ukwuani and Urhobo. This gives Ukwuani and Urhobo users of English greater articulation difficulty. This is relevant information on the differences in the quantity and quality of short, long and central vowels in English if they are to pronounce English words correctly. Even the obviously identical vowels in English are not pronounced the same way always since their pronunciation is often determined by the phonological environments in which they occur.

Learning Problems in the Use of English Vowels by Ukwuani and Urhobo Users of English

/i:/ is longer in 'bead' than in 'beat' because in the former word /i:/ is followed by /d/, a voiced consonant whereas in the later, it is followed by /t/, a voiceless consonant. The Ukwuani and Urhobo L₁ Speaker of English as L₂ are ignorant of the above phonological rule and therefore cannot apply it. Definitely, this ignorance results in incorrect pronunciation of English words by the average Ukwuani and Urhobo L₁ speakers of English as L₂. These approximations inevitably result in production of spoken English which differs from the Received Pronunciation (RP) standard and consequently impedes international intelligibility.

Significantly the Ukwuani and Urhobo L₁ user of English resorts to substitution of items. The deviant pronunciations observed among Ukwuani and Urhobo L₁ speakers of English as L₂ are given below

RP	U.E. (Ukwuani English)
(i.) /i:/ and /i/ are realized as /i/ e.g Seat /si:t/ meat /mi:t/ steal /sti:/	/i/ e.g. */sit/ */mit/ */stil/
Here, there is no pronunciation difference for the Ukwuani L ₁ speaker of English as /si:t/ and /sit/ are realized as /sit/	
(ii.) /ae/ and /a:/ → /a/	
From the above approximation, it is clear that Urhobo and Ukwuani L ₁ speakers of English as L ₂ cannot differentiate between the RP Phonemes given above. This is why they pronounce	

- RP U&U.E
 Cart /ka:t/ as /kat/
 Cat /kaet/ as /kat/
- (iii.) /e/ and /ɜ:/ → /e³/ ()
 Here the Urhobo and Ukwuani L₁ users of English as L₂ cannot differentiate the long central vowel /ɜ:/ and the short front vowel /e/ as such, he/she pronounces:
 RP U&U.E
 Bird /bɜ:d/ as ³b d/
 Death /dɜ:t/ as /det/
 Death /deθ/ as /det/
- (iv.) In RP /ɔ/, /ɔ:/, /ʌ/, /ə/ → /ɔ/ or D (U&U.E)
 Unlinguistically informed Urhobo and Ukwuani users of English as L₂ indicates that the above monophthongs are collapsed into /ɔ/ and /ɒ/. This inevitably gives rise to non-standard pronunciation of English words. Hence:
 RP U&U.E
 Sports /spɔ:ts/ becomes */spɔts/
 Love /lʌv/ becomes */lɔv/
 Visitor /vɪzɪtə/ becomes */vɪsɪtɔ/
- (v.) There is also the approximation of /ə/ as /ae/ as in:
 RP U&U.E
 Sister /sɪstə/ → */sɪstae/
 Teacher /ti:tʃə/ → */tɪtʃa/
 Mother /mʌðə/ → */mɔda/
- (vi.) /eɪ/ → /e/ → /e/
 It should be stated here that vowel /e/ in Ukwuani which is No 3 has the same phonetic form with vowel n.3 of English which is also transcribed as /e/. They are not exactly of same quality. While English vowel No. 3 is found between half close and half open position, the Ukwuani vowel No. 3 /e/ is located in the half open position of the tongue. Put differently Ukwuani /e/ is more open than the English /e/ and their articulations do not lead to the production of similar sound. Therefore:
 Wait /weɪt/ is realized as */wet/
 Waist /weɪst/ is realized as */west/
 Way /weɪ/ is realized as */we/
 Plate /pleɪt/ is realized as */plet/
- (vii.) /əʊ/ → /o/
 The following deviant pronunciation are observed among Ukwuani L₁ speakers of English as L₂:
 No /nəʊ/ → */no/
 Go /gəʊ/ → */go/
 Soap /səʊp/ → */sop/
 So /səʊ/ → */so/
 Boat /bəʊt/ → */bot/
- (viii.) /u/ and /u:/ → /u/
 It is observed that the Ukwuani L₁ user of English as L₂ usually collapses /u/ and /u:/ into /u/. Consequently, the following non-standard are realized as follows:

RP	U.E
Pool /pu:/	*/pul/
Fool /fu:l/	*/ful/
Food /fu:d/	*/fud/
Cool /ku:l/	*/kul/
Stool /stu:l/	*/stul/
Sooth /su:θ/	*/sut/
School /sku:l/	*/sku/
Mood /mu:d/	*/mud/
Loom /lu:m/	*/lum/
True /tru:/	*/tru/

(ix.) /uə/, /iə/, /ɔi/, /ə/ → /a/

There are no diphthongs and triphthong in Ukwuani, the Ukwuani L₁ speaker of English as L₂ only try to approximate the English diphthongs and triphthongs to the nearest vowels in their language. This normally, leads to wrong pronunciation as follows:

R.P	U.E
Power /'pau ə /	*/pawa/
Fire /faiə/	*/faja/
Tyre /taiə /	*/taja/
Oil /ɔil/	*/ɔje/

(x.) /ə/ → /o/

Ukwuani L₁ user of English as L₂ collapses the short schwa sound and realizes it as /o/ as seen in the example below:

R.P	U.E
To /tə/, /tu/	*/to/

Learning Problems in the Use of English Vowels by Urhobo Users of English

From the data available on Urhobo, it is obvious that there will be learning problems for the Urhobo user of English as L₂. The user usually resorts to substitution of items as follows:

a. /ʌ/ is substituted with /ɔ/

RP	U.E
Some /sʌm/	*/sɔm/
Cup /kʌp/	*/kɔp/
Cough /kʌf/	*/kɔf/
Love /lʌv/	*/rɔv/
Brother /brʌðə/	*/tɔf/

b. /ɜ/ -³/ / /, /ɔ/ or /a/

RP	U.E
Firm /fɜ:M/	³ /fm/
Worm /wɜ:m/	*wɔm/
Kernel /kɜ:nl/	*/kɜnj /

c. /ə/ → /a/ or /ɔ/

RP	U.E
Weaker /wi:kə/	*/wika/
Doctor /dɔktə/	*/dɔktɔ
Teacher /ti:tʃə/	*/ti,fa/
Sister /sistə/	*/sista/

- d. /i:/, /i/ is collapsed into /i/ as in
 RP U.E
 Weak /wi:k/ */wik/
 Start /sta:t/ */stat/
- e. /ɔ:/, /ɒ/ realized as /ɔ/
 RP U.E
 Port /pɔ:t/ */pɒt/
 Sport /spɔ:t/ */spɒt/
 Mort /mɔ:t/ */mɒt/
 Court /kɔ:t/ */kɒt/

The difference that occurs may not be that of length alone. Sometimes, the quality of the short vowels that emerge is distinctive from the short English vowels. The collapsing that is done above does not accommodate /e/ because it does not have a long counterpart. Therefore, there is no much problem with the articulation of this vowel. Most of the time, the problem is with the long vowels as can be seen above.

The articulation of diphthongs and triphthongs by the Urhobo users of English follows the pattern adopted in the articulation of glide formations of Urhobo. It is through the deletion and insertion rules. One of the vowels in the sequence is deleted and either /i/ or /w/ is inserted. Most times, the vowel that is supposed to be retained is changed.

Examples include:

- RA U.E
 Fear /fiə/ */fje/
 Sure /suə/ */fʷɔ/
 Fire /faiə/ */faja/
 Pray /prei/ */preia/
 The diphthong that does not pose a problem is /au/

Hierarchy of Difficulties in Ukwuani and Urhobo

The items that pose problems to the Ukwuani and Urhobo users of English do not all have the same level of difficulty. What is done below is a tabular summary of two levels of difficulties – new items and collapsed items. Near or similar items are not represented since these do not pose learning problems.

Table 1: Hierarchy of Learning Difficulties of Ukwuani and Urhobo Speakers of English

Aspect	Sound of Feature	Nature of Difficulty
Vowels	/ʌ/, /ɜ/, /ə/, /ɝ/, /eə/, /uə/, /əu/, /ei/, /eiə/, /aiə/, /ɔiə/, /əuə/	New item: all of these vowels have no similar vowels in Ukwuani and Urhobo languages. The learning of these vowels has higher level of difficulty.
	/i:/, /a:/, /ɔ:/, /u:/	Collapsing: Since the short forms of these long vowels are in Ukwuani and Urhobo, they are simply collapsed into the short forms. They are easier to learn

Source: Field Work, 2023.

Conclusion

The phonological analysis and interpretation carried out here are done through generative phonology. Therefore, this research provides an additional angle through which the transfer features in the spoken English of Ukwuani and Urhobo users can be captured. Furthermore, the use of rule application in Generative phonology also provides a clear view of the learning problems of Ukwuani and Urhobo users of English. For example, the application of the deletion and insertion rules in Ukwuani and Urhobo languages provides us with the underlying reasons why high vowels are deleted when they appear before other vowels. This research has helped in providing a large inventory of Ukwuani and Urhobo segmental phonemes particularly vowels.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, it is therefore, recommended that Ukwuani and Urhobo L₁ users of English as L₂ should make sure that:

1. Conscious efforts are put in place to understand the RP standard articulations of all the English vowels that are not in their phoneme inventories such as long vowels, central vowels, diphthongs that are not available in their inventories and triphthongs
2. The concept of silent letters in the orthography of English is studied and understood.
3. The differences between English and Ukwuani/Urhobo with respect to sound distribution should be studied and understood.
4. The standard pronunciation of all English phonemes is mastered by Ukwuani and Urhobo speakers of English as L₂.
5. The findings of this research should be utilized in teaching other Ukwuani and Urhobo L₁ learners of English
6. Contrastive enquiries into the sound patterns of English and other indigenous languages in Nigeria should also be encouraged as some of the problems discovered for the Ukwuani and Urhobo L₁ speakers or learners of English as L₂ may also be encountered by other sets of L₂ speakers or learners of English.

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